

Prevalence Of Substance Use and Its Associated Risk Factors Among Adolescents in an Urban Area in Odisha – A Cross Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Introduction- Substance use among adolescents has life-threatening consequences in future and also a challenge for policy makers to reduce this burden. This work outlines several important issues related to substance use among adolescents. **Objectives-**(1) prevalence of substance use among adolescents; (2) the presence of risk factors associated with substance use. (3) current preventive interventions for adolescent population. **Materials and Methods-**A cross sectional study was carried out in the urban field practice area of a private medical college with use of a semi structured questionnaire and sample size collected was 350. **Results-**Majority of study population were male (76%) and mean age was 14.6 ± 2.8 years. Prevalence of substance use among adolescents was found to be 22.29%. Maximum were addicted to alcohol (66.6%) followed by Gutkha (44.8%), paan (30.7%), gudakhu (29.4%), cigarette(21.8%),cocaine(2.5%),heroin (1.28%) and bidi (1.28%). Addiction was found more in school dropouts, nuclear family, broken family and problem family background and adolescents from upper-lower socio economic status. **Conclusion -** This challenge of substance use among adolescents requires consistent and unremitting attention in order to execute effective prevention programs with continuous re-evaluation of the situation.

Keywords: Adolescents, Substance use, Risk factors.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood and also a crucial period when all types of developmental and health problems arise. Specifically substance use is a major health issue during adolescence. It has been reported around 5.6% people in the age of 15-26 years using drugs at least once(1). Early substance use increases the likelihood of future physical, mental, and social health problems(2). One of the adverse outcomes of adolescent substance use is the increased risk of addiction in those who start smoking, drinking, and taking drugs before they are of 18 years. Moreover,

most individuals with Substance Use Disorders begin using substances when they are young (3). Substance use disorders amongst adolescents have long-term adverse health effects but can be mitigated with efficient treatment (4). Adolescent substance users suffer risks and consequences on the psychological, sociocultural, or behavioral levels that may manifest physiologically (5). About 3 million deaths worldwide were caused by alcohol consumption alone. The majority of the preventable fatalities linked to alcohol consumption are in India among adolescents (6). So the current study was done with the following objectives -(1) To estimate the prevalence of substance use among adolescents; (2)

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To identify the risk factors associated with substance use and (3) current preventive interventions for adolescent population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted at the Urban field practice area of a private medical college and Hospital, Odisha from October 2021 to April 2022. All the adolescents (both males and females) within the age group of 10-19 years (as per WHO) who were residing in the field practice area of the medical college at least for 1 year and were available during the study period were included in our study. As per a study conducted in West Bengal, the prevalence rate of substance abuse among the adolescents had been found to be 31.25% (7) and considering that we calculate our sample size by applying the formula, $n = z^2pq/d^2$ which was around 350. The adolescent population in the field practice area of private medical college was found to be 3190. Simple random sampling method was followed to draw 350 samples out of a total of 3190 adolescents by using the random number table method. All the study subjects were contacted by house to house visit with the help of our field staff and then after taking the informed consent and those below 12 years of age, parent's consent was taken and then they were interviewed and examined using the pretested

questionnaire. It includes socio demographic profile of the study subjects (Age, sex, education, income, education and occupation etc) and their personal habits about substance use, Data analysis was done using Epi info Software. Appropriate statistical tests like percentages and Chi-square tests were applied to analyze the data.

RESULTS

The present study was conducted in the urban field practice area of a Private Medical college and hospital, Bhubaneswar, Odisha. Table-1 describes the socio-demographic profile of study population. Out of 350 sample size, 76% (266) were males and 24% (84) were females. Maximum study subjects (41.1%) were in the age group of 16-19 years. Majority of study population were Hindu (92.3%) and from a nuclear family: 237(67.7%) followed by 3 generation family: 87 (24.8%) and joint family: 26(7.4%). Around 121(34.57%) adolescents did not continue their study (school drop-out) followed by 107(30.57%) completed primary school, 89(25.4%) in middle school, 16(4.5%) in high school and 17(4.8%) in intermediate and above. Maximum study subjects belonged to upper- lower socio-economic status 217(62%) followed by lower 118(33.7%) and lower-middle class 15(4.29%).

Table -1: Socio-demographic profile of the study population (n = 350)

Variables	Male	Female	Total
Age (Years)			
10-13	65 (24.4%)	46(54.7%)	111(31.7%)
13-16	75 (28.2%)	20 (23.8%)	95(27.1%)
16-19	126 (47.3%)	18(21.4%)	144(41.1%)
	266 (76%)	84(24%)	350(100%)
Religion			
Hindu	248(93.2%)	75(89.2%)	323 (92.3%)
Muslim	12 (4.5%)	5 (5.9%)	17 (4.9%)
Others	6(2.2%)	4 (4.8%)	10 (2.9%)
Type of Family			
Nuclear family	171(64.2%)	66 (78.5%)	237 (67.7%)
Joint family	18 (6.7%)	8 (9.5%)	26 (7.4%)
3 generation family	77 (28.9%)	10 (11.9%)	87 (24.8%)

Education			
Primary	52 (19.5%)	55 (65.4%)	107 (30.57%)
Middle school	67 (25.1%)	22 (26.1%)	89 (25.43%)
High school	14 (5.2%)	2 (2.4%)	16 (4.57%)
Intermediate & above	17 (6.4%)	0 (0%)	17 (4.86%)
Not continued (Drop out)	116 (43.6%)	5 (5.9%)	121 (34.57%)
Socioeconomic status			
Upper	0	0	0
Upper middle	0	0	0
Lower middle	7 (2.6%)	8 (9.5%)	15 (4.29%)
Upper lower	170 (63.9%)	47 (56%)	217 (62%)
Lower	89 (33.5%)	29 (34.5%)	118 (33.7%)

Table -2-Distribution of study subjects as per the presence of substance use among them (n = 350)

Substance Use	Male	Female	Total
Present	57(16.3%)	21(6%)	78(22.3%)
Absent	209(59.7%)	63(18%)	272(77.7%)
Total	266(76%)	84(24%)	350(100%)

Table 2 shows, out of 350 adolescents, 78 (22.3%) adolescents have the habit of substance use. Among them substance use was 57 (16.3%) in male and 21(6%) in female.

Table -3-Distribution of different types of substance use among adolescents in our study-(n=78)

Type of substance use	Male-57 (%)	Female-21 (%)	Total-78 (%)
Alcohol	51 (89)	1 (4.7)	52(66.6)
Gutkha	24 (42.1)	11 (14.1)	35(44.8)
Paan	16 (28)	8 (38)	24(30.7)
Gudakhu	16 (28)	7 (33.3)	23(29.4)
Cigarette	17 (29.9)	0	17(21.8)
Cocaine	2 (3.5)	0	2(2.5)
Bidi	1(1.7)	0	1(1.3)
Ganja	1 (1.7)	0	1(1.3)
Heroin	1 (1.7)	0	1(1.3)

Table 3 explains maximum adolescents were addicted to alcohol 52(66.6%) followed by Gutkha 35(44.8%), Paan 24(30.7%), Gudakhu 23(29.4%), Cigarette 17(21.8%), Cocaine 2(2.5%), Heroin 1(1.3%).

Table -3-Association of demographic variables with substance use among study subjects.

Demographic Variables		Substance use		Total (%)	Chi-square(X ²), d f, P (S/NS)
		Yes (%)	No (%)		
Age (years)	10-13	18 (23.0)	93(34.2)	111 (31.7%)	X ² =4.46 , df=2 ,P=0.108 NS
	13-16	27 (34.6)	68 (25)	95 (27.1%)	
	16-19	33 (42.3)	111(40.8)	144(41.1%)	
	Total	78 (100)	272 (100)	350 (100)	
Sex	Male	57 (73.0)	209(76.8)	266 (76%)	X ² =0.49 , df=1 , P=0.47 NS
	Female	21 (26.9)	63(23.1)	84 (24%)	
	Total	78	272	350	

Religion	Hindu	75 (96.1)	248(91.1)	323 (92.3%)	X ² =2.12 ,df=2 , P=0.34 NS
	Muslim	2 (2.5)	15(5.5)	17 (4.9%)	
	Others	1 (1.3)	9(3.3)	10 (2.9%)	
	Total	78	272	350	
Education	Primary	10 (12.8)	97(35.6)	107 (30.57%)	X ² =87.59 ,df=4 ,P=0.001 , S
	Middle school	3 (3.8)	86(31.6)	89(25.43%)	
	High school	1 (1.3)	15(5.5)	16 (4.57%)	
	Intermediate & above	2 (2.5)	15(5.5)	17 (4.86%)	
	Drop out	62 (79.5)	59(21.7))	121 (34.57%)	
	Total	78	272	350	
Type of Family	Nuclear	46 (58.97)	191(70.2)	237 (67.7%)	X ² =7.32 . df=2 ,P=0.2 S
	Joint	11 (14.1)	15(5.5)	26 (7.4%)	
	3 generation	21 (26.9)	66(24.2)	87(24.8%)	
	Total	78	272	350	
Broken Family	Yes	41 (52.56)	23(8.4)	64 (18.2%)	X ² =78.9 ,df=1 ,P =0.001 ,S
	No	37 (47.4)	249(91.5)	286 (81.7%)	
	Total	78	272	350	
Problem Family	Yes	38 (48.7)	86 (31.6)	124 (35.4%)	X ² =7.78 , df=1 ,P=0.005 , S
	No	40 (51.3)	186 (68.4)	226 ((64.6%)	
	Total	78 (100)	272 (100)	350 (100%)	

df -degree of freedom, S-Significant, NS-Not Significant

Table-4 represents maximum study participants with substance users were between 16-19 year age 33 (42.3%) ,belongs to male 57(73%) and from Hindu religion 75 (96.1%),but there is no significant association found between male and female substance users with these 3 variables(age ,sex,religion),P>0.05.But there is significant association found between substance users with their educational qualification(school drop outs were more addicted 62(79.5%)),from nuclear families 46 (58.97% , from broken families 41(52.56%) and problem families 38(48.71%) (P<0.05).

DISCUSSION

In our study the total number of adolescents were 350. Out of them, majority (41.1%) were in the age group of 16-19 years followed by 31.7% in the age group of 10-13 years and 27.1% in the 13-16 years age group. But as per a study by Readdy AP et al (8), the majority (46.6%) were 11-14 years followed by 15-18 years (38.8%) and 7-10 years (14.6%).

The mean age of participants of our study was 14.6 ±2.8 years where as in another study done by Daniel LT et al (9) in suburban Delhi, the mean age was 15±2.3 years which is similar to our study.

In our study maximum study subjects were male(76%) which is similar to other studies done in West Bengal among high school students (82% were male) and in Jaipur among school children(71% were male adolescents)(10)

Majority of adolescents in our study belonged to Hindu religion (92%), as per a study conducted in Mumbai among street children 66.3% (11) were Hindu and from another study conducted in Dehradun of Uttarakhand done among students shows 90.1% were Hindu (12). In current study ,34.29% adolescents were found to be school dropouts, but as per a study conducted in urban slums of Mumbai,44.2% were school dropouts (11) which was slightly more than our study. In our study majority were from nuclear family (67.7%) which is almost same as per a study conducted by Baba TA, et al at Kashmir valley (maximum from nuclear family- 52.4%) (13).

Maximum study participants belonged to upper lower socio-economic status i.e, 62% followed by lower class 33.7% and lower middle class 4.29%.In a study by Kokiwar PR et.al, 38.5% belonged to upper lower class followed by upper middle class(37.7%).(14)

In current study, 35.4% were from problem families and 18.3% were from broken families. But as per a study done by Sarangi et.al 53% were from problem families (15) which is much higher than our study. Out of 350 study subjects; substance use was present in 78 (22.29%) of adolescents. In a study by Sarangi L et.al, the prevalence of substance use was 43.4% which was higher than our study (15). Mostly adolescents were addicted to alcohol (66.6%) followed by gutkha (44.8%), paan (30.7%), gudakhu (29.4%), cigarette (21.8%), and bidi, ganja, heroin (1.28%). In a study by Kokiwar PR (14), the most commonly used substance was tobacco (60%), followed by alcohol (12.9%) and only one person used ganja and cannabis. In our study there was no significant association found between substance use and age, sex, religion ($P > 0.05$), but significant association was observed between substance use and their educational status, type of families and from broken and problem families ($P < 0.05$). As per a study by Daniel LT et.al (9), educational status and type of family of study subjects had significant association with substance abuse which was also a finding of our current study. The limitation of our study was that all the adolescents of our study area were not interviewed and subject bias was present since the interview was conducted in the home environment and adolescents might not completely tell about all the substances used by them.

CONCLUSION

In our study prevalence of substance use among adolescents was found to be 22.29%. Maximum adolescents were addicted to alcohol (66.6%) followed by Gutkha (44.8%), Paan (30%), Gudakhu (29.4%), Cigarette (21.8%), Cocaine (2.56%), Bidi, Ganja, Heroin (1.28%). Variables like age, sex and religion of study participants had no significant association with substance use was observed in current study ($P > 0.05$). Statistical significant association was observed between substance use and educational qualification, type of family and family background (problem family and broken family) of study subjects ($P < 0.05$). So proper IEC (Information, Education and Communication) activities must be carried out to create awareness about harmful effects of substance use among adolescent population. Proper counseling should be provided to the members,

problem families to reduce the risks of substance use among adolescents. Broken families need social and financial help to reduce the chances of substance use among adolescents.

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